

THE PRINCIPLE OF JUSTICE IN PROTECTING THE EMPLOYMENT RIGHTS OF CIVIL SERVANT LECTURERS ASSIGNED TO PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the condition that before the enactment of Presidential Regulation Number 19 of 2025 concerning Employee Performance Allowances within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology, Civil Servants (PNS) Lecturers assigned to State Universities (PTN) Work Units and Civil Servants Lecturers assigned to Private Universities (PTS) did not receive performance allowances. This study aims to answer the question regarding the ideal model for protecting the employee rights of civil servant lecturers employed in private universities in order to fulfill the principle of justice. This research is a normative legal research using the Philosophical, Legislative, Conceptual, Historical and Comparative Approaches. The legal materials consist of Primary, secondary and tertiary laws collected through library research, using prescriptive normative analysis methods. The results of this study reveal that the ideal model for protecting the rights of civil servant lecturers employed in private universities in order to fulfill the principle of justice is to use a Hybrid Governance Model, namely by integrating the market-oriented model and academic self-governance in the management of higher education. The recommendation that can be given is that the relevant Minister needs to strengthen regulations to ensure that civil servant lecturers employed in PTS receive their rights in full, proportionally, and with dignity in accordance with the principles of justice in law and human rights.

Keywords: Principle of Justice, Employment Rights, Civil Servant Lecturers.

INTRODUCTION

Article 28D paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia states that "everyone has the right to work and to receive fair and proper compensation and treatment in employment relations."

This provision is a guarantee of legal protection by the state for every person. The meaning of the phrase "everyone" is anyone who has the ability, skills and meets the requirements to do decent work, including those who hold the position of State Civil Apparatus (ASN).

State Civil Apparatus (ASN) is divided into 2 (two) types, namely Civil Servants (PNS) and Government Employees with Work Agreements (PPPK). ASN employees are a new term that emerged in Law Number 5 of 2014 as revoked by Law Number 20 of 2023 concerning State Civil Apparatus to accommodate two professions working in government agencies, both at the central and regional levels.

One of these government agencies is the State University. State Universities based on Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education together with Private Universities are given the task of organizing higher education as stated in Article 1 paragraph (7) and paragraph (8)

of Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, namely:

- (1) State Universities (PTN) are universities that are established and/or run by the government.
- (2) Private Higher Education Institutions (PTS) are higher education institutions that are founded and/or run by the community.

In Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, the affairs of implementing higher education autonomy are divided into 2 (two), namely:

- a. The implementation of higher education autonomy according to Article 65 paragraph (1) of Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education can be given selectively based on performance evaluation by the minister to state universities (PTN) by implementing a public service agency financial management pattern or establishing state universities as legal entities to produce quality higher education.
- b. The implementation of higher education autonomy in private higher education institutions (PTS) according to Article 67 of Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education is regulated by the organizing body in accordance with the provisions of statutory regulations.

Furthermore, according to Article 27 paragraph (1) of Government Regulation Number 4 of 2014 concerning the Implementation of Higher Education and Management of Higher Education Institutions, in order to implement PTN autonomy, they can apply the following management patterns:

- a. PTN with a general state financial management pattern (PTN);
- b. PTN with a public service agency financial management pattern (PTN BLU);
- c. PTN as a legal entity (PTN BH).

In providing services, lecturers can be assigned to State Universities and Private Universities as regulated in Article 26 of the Regulation of the State Civil Service Agency of the Republic of Indonesia Number 16 of 2022 concerning Procedures for Determining the Assignment of Civil Servants in Government Agencies and Outside Government Agencies which states that:

- (1) Civil servants with the positions of teachers, lecturers and health workers who carry out duties at schools, universities or private health service units can carry out their duties through assignments in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations.
- (2) The provisions regarding the assignment period and assignment extension do not apply to civil servants as referred to in paragraph (1).
- (3) Decisions on assignments for teachers, lecturers and health workers as referred to in paragraph (1) are determined without going through technical considerations from the Head of the State Civil Service Agency.

- (4) The Parent Agency submits the decision on the Assignment of Civil Servants who occupy the positions of teachers, lecturers and health workers as referred to in paragraph (1) to the State Civil Service Agency.

In order to improve the performance of civil servants, especially lecturers, Presidential Regulation Number 19 of 2025 concerning Employee Performance Allowances within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology was issued. The mandate of this provision is that employees within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology, in addition to being given income in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations, are given a monthly performance allowance.

The provision of performance allowances for employees within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology is given after considering the employee's performance achievements in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations. The number of civil servant lecturers who will receive performance allowances is 31,066 people, with details of 8,725 civil servant lecturers assigned to PTN Satker, 16,549 civil servant lecturers assigned to PTN BLU (who have not received remuneration) and 5,801 civil servant lecturers assigned to PTS. (Kompas, 2025) Furthermore, Article 7 of Presidential Regulation Number 19 of 2025 concerning Employee Performance Allowances within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology states that the performance allowances as referred to in Article 2 are not given to:

- a. Employees within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Technology who do not have a specific position;
- b. Employees within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Technology who are temporarily dismissed or deactivated;
- c. Employees within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Technology who are dismissed from their organic positions and are given waiting money and have not been dismissed as employees;
- d. Employees within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Technology who are on leave without state support or are on leave to prepare for retirement;
- e. Employees of public service agencies who have received remuneration in accordance with the provisions of laws and regulations governing the financial management of public service agencies; and
- f. Employees at state universities that are legal entities.

Based on these provisions, employees (lecturers) at PTN BLU and employees (lecturers) at PTN BH do not receive performance allowances, because they already receive remuneration (Kumparan, 2024) from the agency where the employees (lecturers) work at PTN BLU and PTN BH. According to PNS Lecturers who work at PTN BLU and PTN BH, these provisions constitute an inequality or injustice for PNS Lecturers assigned to PTN BLU and PTN BH, because the remuneration given at a number of PTN BLU and PTN BH is still below the nominal performance allowance stated in the attachment to Presidential Regulation Number 19

of 2025 concerning Employee Performance Allowances within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology. (Kompas, 2025)

Before the enactment of Presidential Regulation Number 19 of 2025 concerning Employee Performance Allowances within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology, Civil Servants Lecturers assigned to PTN Satker and Civil Servants Lecturers assigned to PTS did not receive performance allowances. Performance allowances are part of employee rights as a form of appreciation for performance and to increase productivity. Furthermore, this study will examine the strengths and weaknesses of several technical regulations governing the provision of performance allowances for lecturers within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology. The enactment of Presidential Regulation Number 19 of 2025 concerning Employee Performance Allowances within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology as a legal basis for providing performance allowances still raises various problems that need to be addressed immediately to ensure fairness and equality for all lecturers within the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology.

From the various descriptions, problems arise related to the granting of welfare rights, the autonomy of higher education management includes academic and non-academic fields, according to Article 64 paragraph (3) of Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, it states that management autonomy in non-academic fields includes, among other things, the determination of operational norms and policies and financial implementation. In addition, there is a conflict of norms related to the technicalities of providing *tukin*, namely in Presidential Decree Number 19 of 2025 there is no regulation regarding the provision of 80% or 60% *tukin* for study assignment employees or study leave employees, but in Permendikisintek Number 23 of 2025, especially Article 14 paragraph (1) regulates that the provision of *tukin* for study assignment employees and study leave employees who are still carrying out the obligations of the Tridharma of Higher Education only receive 80% *tukin*, even though in terms of obligations they are the same as employees whose status is not on study assignment or not on study leave, but their rights are different. In addition, in the Minister of Education and Technology Regulation Number 23 of 2025, specifically Article 14 paragraph (2), it regulates the provision of *tukin* for employees on study assignments or employees on study leave who are exempt from the obligation of the Tridharma of Higher Education to receive 60% *tukin*. Therefore, the author will conduct a study related to the ideal model for protecting the employee rights of Civil Servants Lecturers employed at Private Universities in order to fulfill the principle of justice.

RESEARCH METHODS

Normative, namely law is conceptualized as what is written in laws and regulations (law in books) or law is conceptualized as rules or norms that are benchmarks for human behavior that are considered appropriate. (Amiruddin & Asikin, 2004) Normative legal research in this study is supported by a socio-legal research approach. The approaches used are: a philosophical approach, a legislative approach, a conceptual approach, a historical approach, and a comparative approach. The types and sources of data are: primary legal materials, secondary

legal materials, and tertiary legal materials. This study examines secondary data consisting of primary legal materials and secondary legal materials collected using document study techniques. All legal materials obtained are then analyzed and processed using prescriptive normative analysis methods. The conclusion or drawing of conclusions in this study uses a deductive method, namely drawing conclusions from the general to the specific.

DISCUSSION

An Ideal Model for the Protection of Civil Servant (PNS) Lecturer Rights Employed in Private Universities

The determination of a university's status, from work units, public service agencies, and legal entities, represents its identity and symbol of its authority in organizing and governing its institution. The autonomy policy is essentially a product of financial reform aimed at improving the quality of education, ensuring that funding is not confined to a single entity, but rather that universities and the public participate in educational matters. The hope is that the government will benefit from the autonomy policy, as the financial burden is not solely the government's responsibility but rather a shared one. Universities are empowered to generate income to supplement their operational costs, while the public contributes to education as a form of participation in the educational sector.

The autonomy policy first emerged with the aim of reforming the higher education system. This reform policy was implemented extensively after the fall of the New Order. Higher education autonomy was no exception, becoming a priority on the reform agenda. Although the autonomy policy was rolled out after Indonesia became a member of the WTO in 1994, it remained largely unrecognized due to the government's centralistic policies. The core of this educational reform included reforming the national higher education paradigm and decentralizing the national education system to improve relevance and quality.

This policy was originally created to reduce or minimize government intervention in the provision of education. This is in line with WTO policies that demand liberalization of the education sector. The fundamental rationale is that reduced government intervention will foster autonomy and independence for educational institutions, especially higher education. This logic serves as the government's argument for not interfering more in educational affairs but instead handing over educational matters to the public. If the government reduces its intervention in the provision of education, this will actually have a more severe impact on society, as education is no longer considered a basic right for every citizen and is obligated to fulfill it, but instead becomes a commodity.

Ball explained that neoliberalism has infiltrated national education. Whether consciously or not, national education has been moving towards neoliberalism since the reform era. One sign of this is the tendency of various government policies to reduce intervention in developing the world of education. (Adam and Muryanto, 2021) Neoliberalism provides opportunities for individuals to compete and create, while also financing all their own needs. This condition is very contrary to the mandate of the 1945 Constitution which gives the government the

responsibility to allocate funds of at least 20% of the state budget/regional budget for educational development, but on the other hand, neoliberalism emphasizes that government intervention in educational activities must be reduced.

When this autonomy policy emerged, it sparked euphoria among universities. Universities demanded the freedom to manage and administer their institutions independently so as not to burden the government. The fundamental reason for universities was that government bureaucracy was too complicated to meet the needs required by universities to realize the Tridharma of Higher Education. This reasoning became the trigger or catalyst for removing government intervention in the implementation of higher education and handing over management to the public. This was not without reason, as this autonomy policy was a joint effort between the government and universities. This policy was a program initiated by global institutions, particularly the IMF and WTO, aimed at the government and universities as executors in realizing its true intent. Upon closer examination, this policy was actually intended to remove the state's role in regulating educational affairs and hand over education to the public to manage educational institutions. To facilitate this agenda, the government used academics and university bureaucracies to campaign for this autonomy policy, and both academics and university bureaucrats agreed.

The primary reason universities accepted the university autonomy policy was to align their management with that of universities in America and Europe. However, education policies in America and Europe are the result of liberalization initiated by the WTO and the IMF. The goal was to reduce the role of the state as an education provider, while handing over education to the public sector. To reduce the state's role, universities were given the freedom to compete fairly to develop their institutions.

Tilaar explained that the autonomy policy emphasizes competition with other countries, even though the principles of competition and competitiveness are concepts born from neoliberalism, adopted by the World Bank/IMF. Western economic experts have condemned this concept as a failure, as the principle of competition is actually a tool of capitalism for the benefit of developed countries. (Adam and Muryanto, 2021)

The birth of the World Class University concept directs universities to be independent and competitive in the market. In fact, the World Class University concept is actually a privatization concept to make universities follow the currents of globalization. Globalization itself is a mission carried out by the IMF, World Bank, and WTO with the aim of aligning educational development globally. Therefore, to build the world of education, each country must comply with the policies and regulations offered by these global institutions.

Consequently, education must follow market tastes and be handed over to the public to be managed based on the principle of public ownership, so that the community becomes the largest shareholder in contributing to education and the government is free from these matters. Ghosh, argues that higher education, whose management is free from government control, whether the goal is to seek profit or not, is privatization that is reflected in the formulation and implementation of various educational policies. (Adam and Muryanto, 2021)

Universities are given full autonomy to manage their resources as government intervention becomes increasingly minimal. This situation requires universities to manage their own funding. The hope is that universities' dependence on government funding will decrease. Higher education, as a commodity, needs to sustain itself.

When autonomy began to be implemented, there was still much debate within the government, the public, and academics. While everyone hoped that the autonomy policy would provide solutions, it instead created new problems for state universities. Universities were not only required to carry out their duties of educating, but were also burdened with additional burdens and responsibilities, such as finding their own funding and building partnerships to generate income.

The autonomy policy in higher education was initially seen as a solution offered by the government. The government believed that the autonomy policy would provide solutions in education management, ensuring proper management. The autonomy policy was a breath of fresh air for higher education, with the hope that universities would be given the authority to manage their institutions independently. However, after its implementation, the autonomy policy faced resistance.

This reality was evident in the Law on Legal Entities in Education. The Law on Legal Entities in Education was later annulled by the Constitutional Court for violating the state constitution. This was then followed by another policy, Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education. Although its content is not significantly different from the Law on Legal Entities in Education, the Law on Higher Education was nevertheless legalized to fill the legal gap that legitimized the management of higher education.

Autonomy is an inevitability that must be accepted, even though in practice there are still patchworks here and there, but the autonomy policy is considered a final solution. Zainuddin, stated that autonomy is not a "panacea" that can cure current educational problems. In fact, the implementation of the autonomy concept still faces obstacles and problems in its implementation.

If examined further, higher education autonomy can lead to: First, the existence of a lack of coordination, where universities no longer want to be regulated and controlled by the government, in this case the relevant Minister, and they prefer to manage their institutions independently. Second, the emergence of an attitude of arrogance among academics who take advantage of opportunities to compete for power and wealth. Third, the emergence of the idea of prioritizing the interests of each university for the sake of competition. Fourth, there is a separation of territory between society and the world of campus. Fifth, universities tend to exploit students in order to improve the capabilities of the university concerned. (Zainuddin, 2008)

The autonomy policy remains a hot topic of debate due to its unclear direction and ongoing controversy among the public, academics, and education practitioners. On the one hand, the autonomy policy is seen as abdicating the government's role and responsibility in education delivery and handing over its management to the community and universities.

However, on the other hand, the government argues that this autonomy policy aims to develop the world of education so that its management is sound, transparent, accountable, and equitable. Many believe that the autonomy policy diminishes the government's role as the largest stakeholder in education provision. Instead, education management will shift to the responsibility of the community and universities.

Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System and Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, are the legal basis for legitimizing higher education institutions so that their management is regulated autonomously. With this legal basis, higher education institutions are given the option to change their status to a Legal Entity or Public Service Agency. This is as stated in Law Number 12 of 2012 in Article 65 Paragraph (1) which explains that State Universities can implement a financial management pattern of a public service agency or by establishing a State University with a Legal Entity to produce quality higher education. From the explanation of the Law, the content is actually an instruction on the financial management mechanism of higher education institutions, but the status is also attached to the institution or institution.

Darmaningtyas, stated that autonomy with the change of Legal Entity Higher Education Institutions and Public Service Agencies can be said that this policy gives rise to stratification of higher education institutions. The division is based on funding sources, where those that are economically established are given independence, when those that are not economically established then the government controls them in the hope that they can gradually develop independently. (Darmaningtyas, 2015)

This fact is as explained in Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education in Article 62 paragraph (1) to paragraph (4). It explains that higher education institutions have autonomy to manage their own institutions and the basis and objectives of their management are adjusted to the capabilities of the higher education institution and regulated by Ministerial Regulations. The facts show that the government is unable to finance national education, especially higher education. Where before the enactment of the massive autonomy policy, higher education institutions received subsidies from the government of around 75%.

This means that the government provides a larger portion to finance the operational costs of higher education institutions, while the remaining 25% comes from the community including the Single Tuition Fee (UKT) fund. However, the government revoked the subsidy and granted autonomy to higher education institutions to manage their higher education institutions independently. This independence means that higher education institutions are given autonomy to seek funding and manage their respective finances.

The autonomy policy has changed the paradigm of higher education management which was previously the responsibility of the government then changed to the responsibility of the community and also higher education institutions with different portions. This is as stated by Ali Gufron Mukti, who stated that an ideal university is one whose funding management consists of 40% from the government, 30% from student tuition fees, and the remaining 30% for product development (holding). (Adam and Muryanto, 2021)

This change in percentage indicates that the government has abdicated its responsibility for providing education and has instead transferred funding to the community and universities. Universities are then burdened with finding their own funding. If a university lacks commercialized businesses or infrastructure, the option is to increase the Single Tuition Fee for students. Furthermore, universities have the authority to determine tuition rates for each major and each study program, both in the exact sciences and non-exact sciences. These fees also vary depending on the income of the student's parents.

This suggests that universities, as academic institutions, are being managed like corporations or companies. Universities tend to be likened to companies seeking funds to pay their employees and cover operational costs. When university funds are minimal, students become a source of exploitation. The fact remains that universities are still seeking funding from the Single Tuition Fee, while government subsidies have begun to be reduced. This situation is due to the perception among many that providing education subsidies will reduce student-generated revenue. This means that a small amount of student-generated revenue leads to inefficient management of university resources. Both government and university circles consider that the implementation of subsidies at the university level borne by the government is considered a form of inefficiency, so there is a need for cross-subsidies.

The Single Tuition Fee is the sum of all student payments, including lecturers' salaries, learning facilities, building maintenance, electricity, and other expenses. Although the Single Tuition Fee is adjusted based on the student's parents' income, it is subject to annual adjustments and is subject to potential increases.

The paradigm developed by universities and the government has been that if universities are granted autonomy in both academic and non-academic areas, they can manage themselves independently. Universities have the authority to make decisions and implement their own policies. The government only oversees the applicable guidelines. Meanwhile, the government still provides educational funding, but with the assumption that universities can raise some funds themselves. The goal of the autonomy policy is the efficiency of managing state universities. This means that if universities have institutional authority, they can do much to improve quality. Changing the status of universities from work units to public service agencies, or public service agencies to legal entities, is actually a form of effort undertaken by universities to manage themselves independently.

If universities are granted broad authority, the hope is that they will be able to determine their own policies and determine their own costs, thus becoming independent and decentralized. If this occurs, it is feared that new kings will emerge in universities with their own authority. This authority will allow universities to freely determine and enact policies based on their own desires, which could burden the community in continuing their education to the higher education level. However, autonomy policies are currently a necessity for universities and a necessary option to increase efficiency and improve educational quality. Although universities and the public are victims of autonomy policies, these policies must continue to be implemented as a consequence of a country's membership in the WTO.

Since the introduction of autonomy in higher education, the most significant issue has been independence in seeking funding. Universities are required to support themselves without relying on direct government assistance. Universities have taken anticipatory measures to address this policy. The government only provides oversight through a draft law as a legal framework to justify and legitimize university policies.

Universities have increasingly established partnerships with other institutions, built businesses, charged students a single tuition fee, and launched other income-generating ventures. The initial concept of the autonomy policy, which was to improve the quality of education, has been hampered by funding. Ultimately, universities must use the community as an experiment to generate funds. Rahardjo argues that the goal of university autonomy is to improve the quality of education through independence, but this independence is used as a basis for collecting funds from the community at will. (Rahardjo, 2010)

Education liberalization policies continue to emerge and are implemented in various ways. One such approach is the creation of regulations that give rise to legislation, including Law Number 25 of 2007 concerning Investment. This law actually has implications for education management. While this law was originally enacted to regulate business activities, its derivatives ultimately also target the education sector. The enactment of Presidential Decree Number 44 of 2016, a product of several revisions to the Presidential Decree concerning the list of closed business sectors and those open with conditions in the investment sector, states in its appendix that education, including higher education, is a sector open to foreign investment with a percentage of 49%.

This implies that companies may invest in educational institutions to assist them in developing higher education. However, when a company or business sector invests in an institution, its primary focus is profit. The government has provided investors with the opportunity to assist universities through Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, Articles 79 and 86, which stipulate that the government facilitates the business world, industry, and other parties to collaborate or provide financial assistance to universities. (Rahardjo, 2010)

Since the advent of autonomy policies in higher education, the paradigm of university funding has also changed. When autonomy was introduced, universities were expected to be given the authority to manage their institutions in a decentralized manner. However, in reality, autonomy policies are limited to fundraising and financial management. Zainuddin argues that centralization and decentralization in education seem to be indistinguishable, and in fact, they burden society even more. At a time when society needs adequate education, it is also being strangled by high education costs. For the poor, the high cost of education is a particularly painful oppression. (Zainuddin, 2008)

Indonesian universities face increasingly serious funding challenges. This situation is exacerbated by the attitudes and behavior of corrupt state officials, who can influence the management of educational funding policies. Triharso stated that the government bureaucracy is infected with the virulent virus of corruption, collusion, and nepotism. Ironically, universities, especially state universities, are also unable to cope with such national conditions

and are even prone to being swept away by the currents of this chaos. (Triharso, 2015)

Financing for higher education institutions remains far from satisfactory, especially since it lacks adequate institutional infrastructure and human resources. Due to the country's weak financial condition, the paradigm for managing higher education institutions, particularly in terms of funding, has begun to shift. The public and students are beginning to be overlooked and burdened with various funding responsibilities. The government is also allocating relatively less funding for education. Consequently, the government is implementing fiscal policies to reduce government spending. Subsidies for state universities are either reduced or maintained. However, universities are required to improve the quality and service they provide to students. Consequently, state universities are mobilizing funding from various sources, one of the most accessible of which is students. (Zainuddin, 2008)

Fundraising aims to generate Non-Tax State Revenue. Non-Tax State Revenue is used to finance the operational costs of higher education institutions. Currently, Non-Tax State Revenue for state universities is obtained from educational development contributions, entrance examination fees, sales proceeds from higher education institutions, work contracts in accordance with the university's role and function, as well as donations or grants from individuals, government and non-government institutions, and community revenue. Universities are accused of commercializing education because they charge quite high fees. Rahardjo argues that autonomy can make universities increasingly commercial, making certain study programs accessible only to the wealthy. This is evident in the fact that some universities charge very high fees for certain study programs. As a result, only those with deep pockets can enroll in these study programs. Lower-class communities find it difficult to afford them, making education only available to the haves. (Rahardjo, 2010)

The cost of higher education is becoming increasingly unaffordable. The need to improve the education system must be met with the limited funding available from the State Budget for education, particularly higher education. The state's tendency to abdicate its responsibility for financing higher education has had a significant impact, making it increasingly difficult for the poor to access higher education because they cannot afford the increasingly expensive entrance fees or semester fees.

Although the government allocates 20% of the scholarships to the poor, as mandated by Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, through the Bidikmisi program, this program cannot meet the quota. Even this 20% quota is the minimum, and there are concerns that state universities will not meet this minimum. Furthermore, the 20% policy also constitutes discrimination against the community.

The state should have a duty to facilitate all its citizens' access to higher education at affordable costs without discrimination. It should not create regulations that make higher education inaccessible to the wider community. Universities should foster collective intelligence, not partial intelligence. (Triharso, 2015) The ideal model for protecting the rights of civil servant lecturers employed in PTS should use the Hybrid Governance Model, namely by integrating the market-oriented model and academic self-governance in the management of higher

education institutions to comply with the principles of procedural justice and substantive justice through regulatory policies by optimizing several components, namely:

1. Combining a firm normative-legal framework (protection of status and rights) namely legal certainty and administrative protection in principle Civil Servants Lecturers placed in PTS still maintain full Civil Servant status (basic rights, functional allowances, performance allowances, family allowances, pension rights, social security rights), where the protection and fulfillment of these rights should be through legal instruments in the form of Government Regulations or Ministerial Regulations that explicitly regulate the assignment mechanism, the scope of rights maintained, and the limits of responsibility of the assignor/parent agency and PTS. This is an implementation of the Welfare State Theory of Law, namely the state must guarantee the welfare of the apparatus as part of social services and public welfare responsibilities. If linked to Aristotle's Theory of Justice, the certainty of status realizes the proportionality of rewards and John Rawls' Theory of Justice seeks to maintain basic freedoms and the relative position of lecturers;
2. Clear financing and implementation mechanisms (MoU and standardized funding) namely in principle all assignments are accompanied by a tripartite MoU (originating institution-PTS-PNS) which contains financing obligations (additional salary, allowances, facilities, credit point financing), assignment duration, and legal responsibility scheme. In its fulfillment, it can be done through technical provisions stipulated by national MoU clause standards, payment deadlines, administrative sanctions if PTS delays/refuses financial obligations. The link with the Welfare Law State is demanding public fiscal certainty or protection mechanisms so that economic rights are not sacrificed and if linked to Rawls' Theory of Justice, this is to prevent lecturers as the most disadvantaged party;
3. A synchronous credit score recognition system and career system (related to career and meritocracy where the principle is that every academic activity carried out at PTS (teaching, research, community service, publication) must automatically have its credit scores recognized by the central system so that in protecting and fulfilling these rights there is a clear mechanism regarding technical guidelines for submitting and validating credit scores, an independent verification team, and a guarantee that assignments do not delay promotions. This is in accordance with Aristotle's Theory of Distributive Justice that rewards are proportional to contributions and in accordance with Rawls' Theory of Justice, namely that promotion positions remain open and fair.
4. Fair remuneration and social security, in principle, in addition to the basic rights of civil servants, if a PTS accepts lecturers, the PTS and/or parent/supervisory institution in this case LLDIKTI are required to provide additional remuneration equivalent to the extra workload, social security (insurance, pension) must not be cut off. This can be done through a remuneration formula mechanism based on workload and transparent performance indicators, pension protection clauses. In relation to the welfare state, the state is obliged to ensure a decent standard of living, while if it is linked to Aristotle's theory of justice, it is in line with wage proportionality and if it is linked to Rawls' theory of justice, the state must protect those who are most vulnerable;

5. Protection of academic freedom and non-discrimination, namely the guarantee of academic freedom (teaching, research, publication) should not be limited by placement contracts, prohibition of discrimination in access to facilities, funds, and academic rights). This protection and fulfillment is through the mechanism of academic freedom clauses in the MoU, independent oversight (Academic Ombudsman). When linked to Rawls' Theory, there are equal basic rights, namely Economic, Social, and Cultural Human Rights;
6. Complaint, remedy, and law enforcement mechanisms, which in principle regulate a rapid complaint access system (internal administration, mediation, and state administration/judicial proceedings) and restitution in the event of violations. The mechanism establishes a civil servant complaint service center, sets deadlines for resolution, and establishes sanctions for violators. A state governed by the rule of law demands legal certainty and access to enforcement mechanisms, while, when linked to Rawls's theory of justice, it demands procedural fairness.
7. Special protection and compensation mechanisms for the most vulnerable, in principle, support schemes such as family allowances and research scholarships for lecturers in vulnerable socio-economic positions. This aligns with Rawls's principle of justice, which aims to improve the conditions of the least advantaged, requiring the state to intervene to achieve this.
8. Transparency, monitoring, and evaluation indicators, including performance indicators related to payment times, the proportion of credits recognized, the level of complaints/violations, the time it takes to resolve complaints, and lecturer satisfaction. This can be achieved through annual reporting mechanisms, independent audits, and the involvement of professional/lecturer unions. A welfare state based on the rule of law requires public accountability and, when examined from the perspective of Aristotle's theory of justice, demands clear distributive practices.

Examining several components in the model, a legal framework and supporting policies are needed, namely through the formation of Government Regulations (PP) or Presidential Regulations that formulate procedures for assigning civil servants outside government agencies, including rights status, standard MoUs, financing obligations, and credit score recognition. Furthermore, related to external oversight mechanisms, it is necessary to establish an Education/ASN Ombudsman and an audit institution involving lecturers' unions. There is a need for a tripartite work agreement (MoU) that must be published and registered in the national system for transparency.

The operational flow of the model related to the request for assignment of civil servant lecturers in PTS is that it is necessary to make a clear request for assignment of civil servant lecturers submitted by PTS to the parent/supervisory agency in this case LLDIKTI located in each PTS region accompanied by a financing plan, then the assessment and approval of the parent/supervisory agency assesses, approves and prepares the MoU, lecturers are given the opportunity to review the clauses.

Next, registration and validation are carried out, where the MoU is registered in the central system, a credit point validation mechanism is prepared. Then the implementation and payment of remuneration/tukin and fulfillment of rights run according to the clauses, the supervisory agency supervises. Monitoring and evaluation are made in the form of quarterly reports or can also be reports every semester and audits are completed quickly. The state not only guarantees the law but also the welfare of its citizens, including civil servants (ASN). In carrying out its obligations, the state regulates, provides fiscal/administrative instruments, and oversees the assignment of civil servant lecturers to private universities (PTS) to ensure their welfare is not compromised.

The ideal model emphasizes the state's role in financing, establishing MoU standards, and oversight, in line with the state's obligations under the rule of law. Without active state involvement (regulations, funding, and oversight), the economic and social rights of lecturers are easily compromised, thus obligating the state to protect civil servants performing public functions. Departing from Aristotle's Theory of Justice which prioritizes proportionality, which provides internal criteria (who has the right to how much), while Rawls provides a structural principle (if inequality arises, it must be regulated so as not to harm the weak), so that this model provides proportional awards and guarantees of compensation for vulnerable parties.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusions

The ideal model for protecting the rights of civil servant lecturers employed in private universities in order to fulfill the principle of justice is to use a hybrid governance model, namely by integrating the market-oriented model and academic self-governance in the management of higher education.

2. Suggestions

LLDIKTI should optimally protect and fulfill the employment rights of civil servant lecturers employed in private universities so that their assignment to private universities does not result in a reduction in financial rights, career opportunities, or legal protection that violates the principle of justice. Furthermore, regulatory strengthening by the relevant Minister is needed to ensure that civil servant lecturers employed in private universities receive their rights in full, proportionally, and with dignity in accordance with the principles of justice in law and human rights.

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